

Assessment Questionnaire on Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) practices

Start of Block: Cover letter

Intro **Assessment Questionnaire on Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) practices**

Objective: This survey contributes to the research activities of the GOOD project, aiming at creating, implementing and assessing Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) practices.

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Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

What you will be called to do: Your participation in the research is completely voluntary. The questionnaire will take around 10 minutes to complete. You are free to refuse to participate in the research and to withdraw from this study at any time. Your decision to withdraw will bring no negative consequences — no penalty to you.

Confidentiality: You will be assigned a code number that will be used to match your responses to the computer. All information will be recorded anonymously. No one will be able to divulge your name or identify your answers. All information will be held in the strictest of confidence. Results from the research will be reported as aggregate data to the funding agency and will be used for publishing in international peer reviewed journals. At the end of the research period, data will be retained by the researcher and will not be sold to a third party but could be shared for further research. What follows is a list of questions. If you are not willing to participate in this survey, select 'I will not participate' and then click the 'Next page' button. To participate in the survey, select 'I will participate' and click the 'Next page' button:

I will participate (1)

I will not participate (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Assessment Questionnaire on Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) practices Objective: This survey... = I will not participate

End of Block: Cover letter

Start of Block: Socio-demographics and farm

Q1 Year of first income in agriculture

▼ before 1900 (1) ... 2023 (124)

Page Break

Q2 How many owned hectares are devoted to the following farming methods?

Conventional (1) _____

Conventional under transition to organic (2)

Organic (3) _____

Biodynamic (4) _____

Regenerative (5) _____

Agroecological (6) _____

Other (7) _____

Page Break

Q3 What is the gender of the business owner/director?

Male (1)

Female (2)

Other (3)

Page Break

Q4 What is his/her year of birth?

▼ After 2000 (1) ... before 1940 (63)

Page Break

Q5 What is his/her highest education level?

- None (1)
- Primary school (2)
- Secondary school (3)
- High School (4)
- University (5)
- Other (please specify) (6)

Page Break

Q6 How many hectares do you grow in each of the following production destinations?

- Cropland (field crops and vegetables) (1)

- Permanent crops (orchards) (2)

- Permanent grasslands (3)

- Other (4) _____

Q7 How many people from the owner's family work in the activity?

End of Block: Socio-demographics and farm

Start of Block: Intention before nudge

Q8 **Think about your overall production when answering the next questions.** On a scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 7 (completely agree), express your level of agreement with the following statements.

	1 (strongly disagree) (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	5 (5)	6 (6)	7 (strongly agree) (7)
I plan to reduce the use of herbicides this year. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I intend to reduce the use of herbicides over the next 5 years. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I will regularly try to reduce the use of herbicides in the future. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Intention before nudge

Start of Block: Nudge

Q9 The topic of this project is **Agroecological Weed Management**. Agroecological weed management is an approach that focuses on utilizing ecological principles and diverse farming practices to effectively manage weeds without relying heavily on herbicides, resulting in enhanced sustainability, biodiversity, and soil health. Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) practices encompass a range of integrated strategies, such as cover crops, intercropping, grazing, mowing, mulching, mechanical control, false seedbed, bio-based herbicides, automated weed control, targeted herbicide use.

End of Block: Nudge

Start of Block: Intention after nudge

Q10 Think about your overall production when answering the next questions. On a scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 7 (completely agree), express your level of agreement with the following statements

	1 (strongly disagree) (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	5 (5)	6 (6)	7 (strongly agree) (7)
I plan to use Agroecological Weed Management practices this year. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I intend to use Agroecological Weed Management practices over the next 5 years. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I will regularly try to introduce Agroecological Weed Management practices in the future. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Intention after nudge